

Phase transition in ammonium di hydrogen orthophosphate crystals –effect of various molar concentration of amino acid

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Abstract

This paper investigates crystals of Ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate after the addition of L- Phenyl Alanine in three different molar concentrations prepared by the slow evaporation method and characterized by Ultraviolet spectroscopy, Fourier transform of Infrared analysis and Powder X-ray diffraction techniques. We observed all these materials have good absorption and transmission in UV region. As concentration increase, there is a decrease in UV absorption. There is a loss of energy as concentration increased due to the inelastic scattering occurs in UV analysis. The phase transition occurs as we increased the different concentration of L- Phenyl Alanine. For one-mole and two-mole concentration crystal system is monoclinic and for five-mole concentration, the crystal system is orthorhombic. The particle size analyzed by Powder peak pattern of this crystals. The size and strain graph plot of William-Hall plot and crystalline size distribution graph of Warren-Aver Bach method interprets strain coefficient, size coefficient and L-graph of $(\Delta d/d)\%$ versus length of peaks pattern predicted by PXRD data.

Keywords: UV-Vis, FT-IR, PXRD, Williamson-Hall plot, Warren-Aver Bach method.

Reference

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